

A RARE CASE OF ADULT ONSET STILL'S DISEASE IN A YOUNG ADULT: CLINICAL PRESENTATION AND MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Adult Onset Still's disease is a rare systemic inflammatory disorder characterized by high spiking fever, arthralgia or arthritis, sore throat, and elevated inflammatory markers. Because its clinical manifestations overlap with infectious and autoimmune diseases, diagnosis is often challenging and requires careful exclusion of other conditions.

Case Presentation: A 24-year-old male presented with persistent high-grade fever for three weeks associated with generalized weakness, myalgia, sore throat, and intermittent joint pain involving the wrist and knee joints. Physical examination revealed fever, pallor, and mild hepatosplenomegaly with joint tenderness. Laboratory investigations showed anemia, fluctuating leukocytosis, elevated liver enzymes, and markedly increased serum ferritin levels (760.9 ng/mL). Lactate dehydrogenase levels were also

significantly elevated. Based on clinical presentation and laboratory findings, a diagnosis of was established. **Management and Outcome:** The patient was treated with antipyretics, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, and systemic corticosteroid therapy prednisolone. Supportive care and monitoring of clinical and laboratory parameters were continued throughout the hospitalization. Following treatment, the patient showed significant improvement with reduction in fever episodes and relief of joint symptoms. **Conclusion:** This case highlights the importance of considering patients presenting with prolonged fever of unknown origin accompanied by systemic inflammatory features. Early recognition,

exclusion of infectious causes, and prompt initiation of corticosteroid therapy can significantly improve patient outcomes and prevent disease-related complications.

KEYWORDS: Adult-onset Still's disease, Inflammatory disorder, Elevated inflammatory markers, Multisystem involvement.

INTRODUCTION

Adult-onset Still's disease (AOSD) is a rare systemic inflammatory disorder with an unknown etiology. It is estimated to have an incidence of about 55–110 cases per year and a prevalence of 600–800 cases in England. The disease typically presents with intermittent high-spiking fever, arthritis or arthralgia, lymphadenopathy, an evanescent rash, sore throat, and other systemic symptoms. AOSD and systemic juvenile idiopathic arthritis (sJIA) are considered part of the same clinical spectrum but occur at different ages.^[2] The term AOSD is used for patients diagnosed after the age of 16 years, whereas sJIA refers to patients diagnosed at or before 16 years of age. The exact cause of the disease remains unclear; however, it is believed that external triggers—most commonly infections—may provoke an abnormal inflammatory response in genetically susceptible individuals. AOSD is mainly a diagnosis of exclusion, and patients must meet the Yamaguchi criteria while other conditions such as infections, malignancies, and rheumatological diseases are ruled out.^[2]

Eric Bywaters first described the condition in 1971 when he reported 14 adult patients with arthritis and systemic features similar to those seen in systemic juvenile idiopathic arthritis (Still's disease). Initially, it was considered a separate clinical disorder, but it is now widely regarded as part of the same disease spectrum.^[3] Laboratory findings that support the diagnosis include leukocytosis with neutrophilia and markedly elevated serum ferritin levels. Clinicians often rely on the presence of a characteristic evanescent salmon-pink maculopapular rash for diagnosis. Although the typical rash is transient, recent studies have highlighted several atypical cutaneous manifestations associated with AOSD.^[3] These atypical skin findings may occur along with the classic rash or, in some cases, may be the only skin manifestation, which can delay diagnosis due to under-recognition. The objective of this study is to describe three new cases of AOSD with atypical skin features and to review the clinical spectrum of atypical cutaneous manifestations reported in this disease.^[2]

EPIDEMIOLOGY

AOSD is a rare condition and is often difficult to diagnose. Currently, there is no clear consensus regarding its incidence and prevalence across different populations. In India, adult-onset Still's disease is considered uncommon, with the prevalence estimated to be less than 1 case per 100,000 people.^[3]

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The pathophysiology of Adult-Onset Still's Disease is mainly associated with an imbalance between the innate immune system and the adaptive immune system. This imbalance results in excessive production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, which play a key role in the development and progression of the disease.^[7] Cells of the innate immune system, particularly macrophages and neutrophils, play an important role in initiating the inflammatory process. These cells contain Toll-like receptors (TLRs) that recognize danger signals such as damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) and pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs). Recognition of these signals activates intracellular inflammatory pathways and leads to the release of multiple inflammatory mediators.^[6]

Neutrophils are especially significant in AOSD. Their activation leads to the release of enzymes and antimicrobial proteins that amplify the inflammatory response. Many patients with AOSD show neutrophilic leukocytosis, which refers to an increased number of neutrophils in the bloodstream.^[3] Activated neutrophils can also release neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs), which further stimulate macrophages and promote cytokine production through activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome. This process increases the production of cytokines such as IL-1 β and IL-18.^[3]

At the same time, macrophages become highly activated and release additional inflammatory mediators through intracellular signaling pathways such as NF- κ B. Increased macrophage activity is also associated with elevated markers including macrophage migration inhibitory factor (MIF), macrophage colony-stimulating factor (M-CSF), and soluble CD163. These markers are often associated with the markedly elevated ferritin levels commonly observed in AOSD.^[5]

In addition to the innate immune response, the adaptive immune system also contributes to the disease process. T helper cells (CD4+ T cells) become activated and may produce

different immune response patterns that further promote inflammation. The interaction between innate and adaptive immune mechanisms ultimately results in the excessive production of several pro-inflammatory cytokines.^[4]

The combined effect of these immune responses leads to overproduction of cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, IL-17, TNF- α , and IFN- γ . Excessive levels of these cytokines can trigger an intense inflammatory reaction known as a cytokine storm, which contributes to the severe systemic manifestations seen in Adult-Onset Still's Disease.^[6]

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 24-year-old male patient presented to the medicine department with complaints of persistent high-grade fever for nearly three weeks associated with generalized weakness, body pain, and reduced appetite. The patient also reported intermittent joint pain involving the wrist and knee joints along with episodes of sore throat and fatigue. There was no prior history of autoimmune disease, tuberculosis, or chronic infection.

The fever was described as intermittent with spikes occurring mainly during evening hours and was partially relieved with antipyretics. The patient also complained of myalgia and progressive weakness over the past few weeks. There was no history of weight loss, chronic cough, hemoptysis, or exposure to infectious diseases.

Initial evaluation for infectious causes including bacterial infections and brucellosis was performed and found to be negative. Due to persistent fever and elevated inflammatory markers, further evaluation was carried out to rule out autoimmune and inflammatory disorders.

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS AND ON EXAMINATION

On physical examination, the patient was conscious and oriented. he appeared febrile and moderately ill.

Vital signs were as follows

Temperature: 38.8°C

Pulse rate: 102 beats/min

Blood pressure: 110/70 mmHg

Respiratory rate: 20 breaths/min

General examination revealed pallor and mild hepatosplenomegaly. No significant lymphadenopathy was observed.

Musculoskeletal examination revealed tenderness and mild swelling over the wrist and knee joints with restricted movement due to pain. No deformities were noted.

Cardiovascular, respiratory, and neurological examinations were otherwise within normal limits.

Considering the clinical features of prolonged fever, arthralgia, sore throat, and elevated inflammatory markers, a provisional diagnosis of Adult-Onset Still's Disease was considered after excluding infectious, malignant, and other autoimmune causes.

LABORATORY INVESTIGATIONS

Laboratory investigations revealed the following findings:

Laboratory Parameter	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	10.1	7.8	9.0	8.1
MCV (fL)		71.4		
MCH (pg)		22.4		
Total Leukocyte Count (cells/mm ³)	6010	7260	4790	1620
Platelet Count (lakh/cumm)	0.57	0.32	0.75	1.02
RDW-CV (%)	18.1			
Random Blood Sugar (mg/dL)	173			
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)			170	
Triglycerides (mg/dL)			139	
LDL (mg/dL)			70	
HDL (mg/dL)			37	
VLDL (mg/dL)			48	
Serum Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.1	0.8	0.5	0.5
Serum Urea (mg/dL)	66	20	16	14

AST (U/L)	28.2			
ALT (U/L)	64.5		67	44
Total Bilirubin (mg/dL)	4.0		5.8	5.7
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	766.9			
LDH (U/L)	1997			
CSF Protein (mg)	20	40	60	80
CSF Sugar (mg/dL)	40	48	55	62
CSF Cell Count (cells/cumm)	70	70	70	70
CSF Culture	No Growth			

Additional tests including brucella agglutination test were negative.

Marked hyperferritinemia along with systemic inflammatory features strongly supported the diagnosis of Adult-Onset Still's Disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The patient was managed with a multidisciplinary approach focusing on control of systemic inflammation.

Pharmacological management included

Inj. Levetiracetam 500mg BD given as stat dose for 15 days

Inj. Pantoprazole 40mg OD given for 15 days

Inj. Ondansetron 4mg TID given for 8 days

Inj. Ceftriaxone 2gm BD given for 5 days

Inj. Paracetamol 1gm given as stat for 15 days

Inj. Doxycycline 100mg BD given for 9 days

Inj. Acyclovir 500mg BD given for 14 days

Inj. Multi vitamin injection OD for 13 days

Inj. Dexamethasone 8mg TID given for 13 days

Inj. Artesunate stat dose for 3 days

Inj. Mucinac 600mg TID given for 15 days

Inj. Tranexamic acid 1gm stat for 6 days

Syp. Lactulose 10ml TID given for 9 days

Inj. Methyl prednisolone 40mg OD given for 5 days

Inj. Cefotaxime 2gm BD given for 8 days

Supportive care including adequate hydration and nutritional support was also provided.

The patient was monitored for clinical response and laboratory parameters. Following corticosteroid therapy, fever spikes gradually subsided and joint pain improved significantly.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Adult-Onset Still's Disease is a rare systemic inflammatory disorder characterized by high spiking fever, arthritis or arthralgia, sore throat, and elevated inflammatory markers. The exact etiology remains unknown, but dysregulation of the innate immune system is believed to play a significant role.

Diagnosis is primarily clinical and requires exclusion of infectious, malignant, and other autoimmune conditions. Hyperferritinemia is considered a key laboratory marker and is frequently observed in patients with AOSD. Elevated liver enzymes and leukocytosis are also common findings.

In the present case, the patient exhibited typical features including persistent fever, arthralgia, elevated inflammatory markers, and markedly raised serum ferritin levels. Infectious causes were excluded through microbiological investigations.

Corticosteroids remain the mainstay of treatment for moderate to severe disease and are effective in controlling systemic inflammation. Early diagnosis and prompt treatment are important to prevent complications such as macrophage activation syndrome, chronic arthritis, and organ involvement.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the importance of considering Adult-Onset Still's Disease in patients presenting with prolonged fever of unknown origin and systemic inflammatory manifestations. Early recognition and timely initiation of corticosteroid therapy can significantly improve clinical outcomes and prevent disease-related complications.

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